

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

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A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“AFFECTION WITH LIANGA”

Life goes on with equilibrium
When I met someone along the shoreline
She's got a touch of beauty
Simple but glamorous of a kind

I am sure my heart beats for her
The sweet smiles from her lips
The expression of humility from her eyes
The innocent look that blazes beyond

Admiration that comes from within
Awakens my lonely broken heart in slumber
With a good and honourable intention
How I wish that treasure would be mine forever

Never in my dream to see even resemblances
That will transform my apathy to inspiration
But Lianga reminds me of the past
So cool, gentle, and affectionate

Great and wonderful are your splendour
The passion of your sea breeze
That blows to touch the green meadows
As I reminisce the memories in solitude

Amidst the dust that bids the daylight
The gem still sparkles in the night
Slowly the full moon appears
To brighten the beauty over the sea

Categories

Please **HIGHLIGHT** the category that best fits your submission:

- ◆ Poetry
- ◆ Short Stories

- ◆ Essays
- ◆ Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- ◆ Creative Corner
- ◆ Others: _____ (Please specify)

After you fill this out, kindly send it to our official email at **binasbookers2013@gmail.com**. Make sure that your work is final before you send it, as any revisions will no longer be accommodated once the process starts. The entire publication will be posted on our official site once it is finalized, at this link:

<https://sites.google.com/view/binasbookers2013/home>.

The online publication process typically takes **7 to 10 days**. However, if you opt for a publication that includes **peer review**, the timeline may vary depending on the availability of reviewers. We appreciate your patience and understanding in this matter.

If you want a hand-signed certificate, we can provide you with a copy. However, you will be responsible for the shipping fee: **₱450 for Luzon, ₱300 for Visayas, and ₱450 for Mindanao**.

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